

First isolation of koi herpes virus (KHV) in Italy from imported koi (*Cyprinus carpio koi*)

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Abstract

The present work describes the first Italian koi herpes virus (KHV) outbreak where the infectious agent was isolated and genetically characterized. At the beginning of April 2012, a batch of koi (*Cyprinus carpio koi*) was imported from Israel by a wholesale facility located in North-Eastern Italy. Fish, originating from different farms, were shipped separately but maintained together in the same tank upon arrival. Three weeks after the introduction of fish, an increased mortality was recorded. Typical clinical and pathological signs of koi herpesvirus disease (KHVD) were observed: enophthalmia, skin erosion, gill hemorrhages and necrosis, pale and enlarged kidney. The histological analysis of symptomatic koi allowed the detection of typical pale intranuclear inclusions in gill epithelium, intestinal lamina propria and kidney. Viral isolation yielded positive results and KHV isolation was confirmed by immunofluorescence. Conventional and real time PCR substantiated the presence of Cyprinid Herpesvirus type 3 (CyHV-3) belonging to the U/I lineage. Mortality in the koi tank reached 82.5% and the few surviving fish were culled by the Official Veterinary Inspector. Epidemiological data and laboratory results suggested that the virus likely originated from Israel.

Introduction

Cyprinid herpesvirus 3 (CyHV-3), commonly known as koi herpes virus (KHV), is the causal agent of a fatal disease known as koi herpesvirus disease (KHVD) that affects common and koi carp (*Cyprinus carpio carpio* and *Cyprinus carpio koi*). KHV is spread worldwide and in Europe it has been extensively described in the UK, France, The Netherlands, Poland,

Germany, Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic and Denmark (Michel et al., 2010; Eide et al., 2011; Olesen and Nicolajsen, 2012). After its first detection in 1998 (Hedrick et al., 2000), the disease spread rapidly through countries and continents, mainly via live fish movements (Taylor et al., 2010). Since KHV infection may persist in latency in infected fish, ornamen-

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tal fish are to date considered as vector of the disease in a naïve country (Peeler et al., 2008) taking into account that they are more likely to travel extensively.

Vaccination against KHV is not allowed within the EU as the disease is included in Annex IV Part II of the European Directive 2006/88/EC. However, a vaccine containing an attenuated deleted KHV strain is widely used in Israel, where the disease is endemic. Ornamental vaccinated fish are allowed to be imported and thus enter the EU countries despite the risk of introduction of vaccinated as well as infected fish, as occurred in the UK. Co-infection of wild type and deleted KHV strains in vaccinated and clinically healthy fish has been reported and is not unusual (Peeler et al., 2008).

In Italy, koi carp rearing as a hobby has increased in the last decade, however, official data on the volume of ornamental fish trading are not available.

The first KHVD outbreak in Italy dates back to 2002 (Haenen et al., 2004). Diseased fish which had been imported from the UK some weeks before the mortality event (80-100% dead fish) were collected from a koi carp pond. The diagnosis was made by electron microscopy and histology while virus isolation tested negative. Another KHVD outbreak was observed in 2008 in an ornamental wholesaler importing koi from Singapore (Gobbo et al., 2008). On this occasion the disease was diagnosed by PCR only and molecular results were confirmed by the University of Wageningen. In the wild, few suspected outbreaks have occurred in more recent years in small ponds with a history of mortality of wild common carp (*Cyprinus carpio carpio*)

(Bovo, personal communication), although in these outbreaks neither viral isolation nor PCR yielded positive results for KHV.

The present paper describes the first Italian KHV outbreak, where typical clinical and pathological signs of KHVD were observed and the infectious agent was isolated and genetically characterized.

Material and methods

At the beginning of April 2012 a batch of 109 koi (*Cyprinus carpio koi*) was imported from Israel by a fish wholesale facility located in North-Eastern Italy. The plant consisted of two greenhouses with a total of 300 tanks with a capacity of approximately 200 l per tank, plus 10 bigger 3m³ tanks. The fish originated from three different Israeli farms: n=67 small size koi (20-25 cm in length) and n=28 medium size koi (25-30 cm in length) came from two different KHV-free farms, while n=14 large size koi (>35 cm in length) originated from a farm where vaccination is routinely carried out and therefore they had presumably been vaccinated. Fish, shipped separately, were subsequently reared in the same tank at 18°C. Four fish of the bigger size jumped outside the tank during the first night after arrival and were found dead the day after and stored at -20°C.

Three weeks later, when the water temperature rose up to 20-22°C due to warm spring weather, an increasing mortality in the small and medium-sized fish was observed. The official inspector was called and necropsy on lethargic specimens (n=3) performed in the field, revealed typical KHV gill and skin lesions. Samples were immediately transported to the laboratory for confirmatory diagnosis and fish

movements to and from the farm were discontinued as required by the European Directive 2006/88/EC. In the following days, the mortality rate increased, reaching 82.5 % by the end of April. Seven days after the first suspect case and the confirmation of KHV diagnosis, all the surviving koi (n= 19) were euthanized and sent to the laboratory for further investigations. After the first detection of clinical signs, the official inspector carried out an accurate epidemiological investigation, collecting information on animal movements and possible indirect contacts with other farms, in order to establish the origin of infection and the farms at risk.

Moribund and euthanized koi underwent necropsy, parasitological and histological examination according to standard procedures. Bacteriological examination of kidney, spleen and brain was performed only for the 3 specimens sampled at the beginning of the outbreak; identification of isolates was performed applying standard culture methods and biochemical assays (Buller, 2004). Gill and kidney samples were collected for virological examination and subjected to nested PCR (Bercovier et al., 2005) and/or real time PCR (Gilad et al., 2004). Molecular characterization of virus was performed by PCR amplification and sequencing of Marker I and Marker II (Bigarrè et al., 2009). Briefly, total DNA was purified using the High Pure PCR template preparation kit (Roche) and PCRs were carried out in singleplex using the oPVP53-oPVP54 primer set for Marker I (ORF 29-ORF 31), the oPVP55-oPVP56 primer set for Marker II (ORF 133) and the AmpliTaq Gold (Applied Biosystems). Amplicons were purified with ExoSAP-IT (USB Corporation, Cleveland, OH) and subsequently sequenced with the same primers using the Big Dye Terminator v3.1 cycle

sequencing kit (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA). Sequencing reactions were cleaned-up using the Performa DTR Ultra 96-well kit (Edge BioSystems, Gaithersburg, MD) and analyzed on a 16-capillary ABI PRISM 3130xl Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). Obtained sequences were assembled and edited with the SeqScape_software v2.5 (Applied Biosystems) and were subsequently aligned with nucleotide sequences related to KHV reference genotypes using the MEGA 4 package.

Positive PCR samples were inoculated in permissive cell culture (CCB - common carp brain - Neukirch and Kunz, 2001) for virus isolation attempt, according to standard procedures (OIE 2012). Briefly, gill and kidney were homogenized and diluted 1:5 in Minimum Essential Medium (MEM) with antibiotics and supplemented by 10% fetal bovine serum and 1% HEPES buffer. After centrifugation, the samples were kept overnight at 4°C and then inoculated into 24 well plates containing CCB cell monolayers (1 ml / well). The plates containing the cultures were incubated for 7 days at 25°C and examined daily for cytopathic effects (CPE) by light microscopy. Immunofluorescence was performed as a confirmatory test on any cell culture showing CPE, using hyper immune rabbit sera produced in house.

Sera samples were collected in all the surviving fish at stamping out time and were analyzed by plaque neutralization according to the protocol developed during the EPIZONE project (Vendramin et al., 2011). Samples with a neutralisation titre higher than 1:80 were considered positive.

Results

During the outbreak of the disease only small and medium koi showed evident clinical signs and died, while larger koi showed milder or no clinical signs. At stamping out time only 19 fish (9 small/medium and 10 large size) were found alive, thus the cumulative mortality rate during the outbreak was 82.5 %, but was 90.5% for small/medium and 28.5% for large koi if calculated according to fish size.

At external examination diseased fish showed: enophthalmus, patches of sandpaper skin (rough texture due to loss of superficial mucus and epithelial erosion), hemorrhagic suffusion of the abdomen, caudal and pectoral fins (Figure 1A and 1B). Gills varied from pale and anemic to congested with hemorrhages, with overproduction of mucus. Generalized gill necrosis was observed in the majority of the fish (Figure 1C). Hemorrhages and telangiectatic vessels of the gill primary and secondary lamellae were present also in large size koi. Notched nose with concavity of the nasal profile was seldom observed in small size koi (probably due to dehydration). Internally, pale and hypertrophic kidney was observed, empty gut with congestion of intestinal vessel was also present. Small and medium size koi showed typical lesions related to KHV infection, while elder koi presented more subdued lesions, mainly erosive and hemorrhagic, which can be related to concomitant parasitic infestation (Figure 1D).

Fresh mounts of gill tissue revealed heavy infestation with *Ichthyobodo necator*, *Ichthyophthirius multifiliis*, *Dactylogyrus* sp. at the time of the first necropsy; *Gyrodactylus* sp. were present in the cutaneous mucus. Necrotic patches of gill tissue revealed filamentous bacteria referable to the

Flavobacterium genus. Formalin and potassium permanganate permanent bath treatment was administered until the confirmation of CyHV-3. *Aeromonas sobria* was isolated from the kidney and spleen of 2/3 specimens.

Histological analysis of small size symptomatic koi sampled at the beginning of the outbreak reported the detection of characteristic pale intranuclear inclusion in gill epithelium with margination of chromatin (Figure 2A). Necrosis of gill epithelium was extensively present and an abundance of ectoparasites (*I. necator*, *I. multifiliis* and *Dactylogyrus*) associated with epithelial hyperplasia, fusion of secondary lamellae and leucocytes infiltration was observed.

Gill arches with macroscopically evident necrosis revealed partial loss of primary lamellae and haemorrhages with presence of mixed colonies of filamentous and coccoid bacteria. Margination of chromatin was sporadically detected also in interstitial lymphoid tissue of the trunk kidney and in leucocytes in intestinal lamina propria (Figure 2B and 2C).

Samples obtained from euthanized small size specimens (later stage infection) revealed fusion of secondary lamellae, hypertrophy and degeneration of gill epithelium with pyknotic and karyorrhectic nuclei, heavy lymphocytes infiltration, haemorrhages and telangiectatic capillaries of secondary lamellae. Mild infestation by *Dactylogyrus* sp. were still present. Lymphoid tissue of trunk kidney exhibited nuclear pyknosis (Figure 2C). Microscopic observation of gills from big size specimens confirmed the telangiectatic capillary dilatation of secondary lamellae, whereas necrotic degeneration of gill epithelium seen in small size koi was

Figure 1. Gross lesions of KHV infected fish. A: enophthalmus; B: hemorrhagic suffusion of the abdomen; C: localized necrotic foci of gills (the first gill arch has been removed); D: pale kidney.

not detected. Sporadic *I. multifiliis* trophonts were present.

A positive real time PCR reaction was found in 19/23 gill and in 6/23 kidney samples tested. The majority of real time PCR positive samples were confirmed by nested PCR. Samples collected from the four large fish which had jumped out of the tank the first day after importation yielded positive real time PCR results.

Viral isolation was successful only for a few samples inoculated immediately after collection, all samples stored at -80°C did not produce CPE in cell culture. In the positive samples,

CPE was observed 3 days post infection and characterized by giant syncytia. The identity of the isolates was confirmed by IF and PCR (Figure 2D).

Serologically, 12/16 fish yielded positive results. Small/medium koi displaying overall lower antibody levels than elder ones (data not shown).

The genetic characterization of KHV viral isolates was performed by amplifying Marker I and Marker II. Primer sets oPVP53-oPVP54 and oPVP55-oPVP56 yielded PCR products of 130 bp-long and 278 bp-long, respectively. Sequence analysis showed deletions in all of the

Figure 2. Microscopic lesion of KHV infected fish: A: gill epithelium displaying characteristic pale intranuclear inclusions (arrows) with margination of chromatin (E&E, 40X); B: leucocytes in the intestinal lamina propria showing typical intranuclear inclusions (arrows) (E&E, 40X); C: lymphoid tissue of trunk kidney exhibiting nuclear pyknosis (arrows) in the later stage of infection (E&E, 40X); D: Fluorescent foci of KHV infected CCB cells 72 h post infection (20X).

three domains within Marker I and Marker II, thus indicating that the KHV isolated in Italy belongs to the United States/Israel lineage (I-/II) according to Bigarrè's classification (Bigarrè et al., 2009).

The epidemiological investigation discovered that, before the suspicion of a notifiable disease and the consequent application of restriction measures on fish movements, 2 batches of 3 and 10 koi respectively were sold to two different ornamental fish retailers in the North East of Italy; a recall of those fish was immediately

made after KHV was first suspected. Fish were euthanized and the fish retailers reimbursed. After the laboratory confirmation of KHV infection, the farm was declared infected and the Competent Veterinary Authority notified to the Ministry of Health. The tank where the infected fish was kept were emptied, cleaned and disinfected, equipment and other fomites were cleaned and disinfected and contaminated materials were removed and destroyed.

Discussion

The importation of koi carp for ornamental

purposes is a very common scenario in Italy, as well as in other European countries. The impact of this activity and its consequences for the introduction of KHV in England and Wales has been thoroughly investigated (Peeler et al., 2008). In this risk assessment, the authors concluded that the likelihood of establishment of KHV into freshwater by importation of a single fish box is quite low, but due to the high volume of traded fish, a certain number of KHV outbreaks per year in imported fish can be expected. Unfortunately, no similar risk assessments have been conducted for Italy, but it can be assumed that the scenario will not differ too much in our country.

In the outbreak herein described, a classical KHVD was observed. In this episode, elder carp showed no or mild clinical signs and only some of them died accidentally, while small/medium sized carp were severely affected by the disease, giving more credibility to the hypothesis that the elder carp were vaccinated prior to transport. Unfortunately, all the efforts to detect the vaccine KHV strain DNA (KV3) failed (data not shown), and therefore whether or not the large size koi were vaccinated could not be definitively ascertained. The laboratory testing reported that the elder carp were less frequently positive (by real time PCR) and showed higher serological titers against KHV compared to younger fish. These results, together with the positive real time PCR reaction detected in fish early after their arrival, suggests that the carp were already infected before being shipped. Laboratory results were therefore in agreement with the epidemiological information retrieved by the official veterinary inspectors, confirming that the viruses under examination had more than likely originated from Israel.

The rapid detection of the KHVD outbreak (within 7 days from importation) allowed the recall of fish that had already been sold to retailer shops, thus minimizing the risk of further spread of the disease. Unfortunately, it was not possible to test the recalled fish, but some of them were already dead prior to being recalled. Thus, although European Council 2006/88/EC art. 2 does not apply to ornamental wholesalers, it is important to keep/establish a basic health monitoring system in this sector in order to prevent any spread of viral pathogens.

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References

- Bercovier H, Fishman Y, Ronen Nahary R, Sharon Sinai S, Zlotkin A, Eryngo M, Oren Gilad O, Eldar A and Hedrick HP (2005). Cloning of the koi herpesvirus (KHV) gene encoding thymidine kinase and its use for a highly sensitive PCR based diagnosis. *BMC Microbiology* **5**, 13–22.
- Bigarré L, Baud M, Cabon J, Antychowicz J, Bergmann SM, Engelsma M, Pozet F, Reichert M and Castric J (2009). Differentiation between Cyprinid herpesvirus type-3 lineages using duplex PCR. *Journal of Virological Methods* **158**, 51–57.
- Buller NB (2004). Bacteria from Fish and Other Aquatic Animal. A Practical Identification Manual. CABI Publishing ISSN/ISBN H ISBN 9780851997384.
- Council directive 2006/88/EC of 24 October 2006 on animal health requirements for aquaculture animals and products thereof, and on the prevention and control of certain diseases in aquatic animals.

- Eide KE, Miller-Morgan T, Heidel JR, Kent ML, Bildfell RJ, LaPatra S, Watson G and Jin L (2011). Investigation of Koi Herpesvirus Latency in Koi. *Journal of Virology* **85**, 4954–4962.
- Gilad O, Yun S, Zagmutt-Vergara FJ, Leutenegger CM, Bercovier H and Hedrick RP (2004). Concentrations of a koi herpesvirus (KHV) in tissues of experimentally infected *Cyprinus carpio* koi as assessed by real-time TaqMan PCR. *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms* **60**, 179–187.
- Gobbo F, Vascellari M, Rampazzo E, Cappelozza E, Manfrin A, Rosteghin M and Bovo G (2008). Identificazione di Koi Herpesvirus (KHV) in carpe koi (*Cyprinus carpio* var. *koi*) importate da Singapore. XV Convegno nazionale della Società Italiana di Patologia Ittica, Erice 22-24, ottobre 2008, p18 (*in Italian*).
- Haenen OLM, Way K, Bergmann SM and Ariel E (2004). The emergence of koi herpesvirus and its significance to European aquaculture. *Bulletin of the European Association of Fish Pathologists* **24**, 293–307.
- Hedrick RP, Gilad O, Yun S, Spangenberg JV, Marty GD, Nordhausen RW, Kebus MJ, Bercovier H and Eldar A (2000). A herpesvirus associated with mass mortality of juvenile and adult koi, a strain of common carp. *Journal of Aquatic Animal Health* **12**, 44–57.
- Michel B, Fournier G, Lieffrig F, Costes B and Vanderplasschen A (2010). Cyprinid herpesvirus 3. *Emerging infectious diseases* **16**, 1835–1843.
- Neukirch M and Kunz U (2001). Isolation and preliminary characterization of several viruses from koi (*Cyprinus carpio*) suffering gill necrosis and mortality. *Bulletin of the European Association of Fish Pathologists* **21**, 125-135.
- OIE Manual of Diagnostic Tests for Aquatic Animals 2012, Chapter 2.3.6. — Koi herpesvirus disease. Available at http://www.oie.int/fileadmin/home/eng/health_standards/aahm/2010/2.3.06_khvd.pdf
- Olesen NJ and Nicolajsen N (2011). Overview of the disease situation and surveillance in Europe in 2011. Proceeding 16th Annual Meeting of the National Reference Laboratories for Fish Diseases Aarhus, Denmark, May 30-31, 2012, p12. Available at http://www.crl-fish.eu/upload/sites/eurl-fish/activities/annual_meetings/16_am_report.pdf.
- Peeler E, Way K and Oidtmann B (2008). An assessment of the impact of importing carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) vaccinated against KHV on the site level prevalence of Koi Herpesvirus in England and Wales. Available at <http://www.docstoc.com/docs/60954409/The-introduction-of-carp-vaccinated-against-KHV-from-Israel>
- Taylor NGH, Way K, Jeffery KR and Peeler EJ (2010). The role of live fish movements in spreading koi herpesvirus throughout England and Wales. *Journal of Fish Diseases* **33**, 1005–1007.
- Vendramin N, Rampazzo E, Cappelozza E, Bovo G, Terregino C and I. Capua (2011). Koi herpes virus: experimental trial, sample collection and development of serological techniques. 12° Fish Immunology Workshop, 17-21 April 2011, Wageningen, The Netherlands.